

Clinical Aid in Pediatric Dentistry: Techniques for Band Stabilization in Impressions

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Abstract:

Background: Accurate dental impressions are vital in pediatric dentistry for diagnostic and therapeutic procedures. However, standard impression trays often cause discomfort and anxiety in young patients, potentially compromising impression quality. Custom-fitted bands offer a potential solution to enhance both the quality of impressions and patient comfort. This study aimed to compare the quality of dental impressions and patient comfort between custom-fitted bands and standard impression trays in a pediatric population.

Methods: Fifty pediatric patients aged 3 to 14 years were included. The study assessed the quality of impressions and patient comfort using custom-fitted bands and standard trays. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, employing t-tests and chi-square tests to determine statistical significance.

Results: The custom-fitted bands technique produced significantly higher quality impressions (mean score: 8.4) compared to standard trays (mean score: 6.9) ($p < 0.01$). Additionally, patients reported higher comfort levels with custom-fitted bands (mean score: 8.1) versus standard trays (mean score: 6.3) ($p < 0.01$). The chi-square tests confirmed significant associations between the stabilization technique and high-quality impressions ($p < 0.05$) and high comfort scores ($p < 0.01$).

Conclusion: Custom-fitted bands significantly improve the quality of dental impressions and enhance patient comfort compared to standard impression trays in pediatric dentistry. These findings suggest that custom-fitted bands should be considered for routine use in pediatric dental procedures.

Recommendations: Future research should explore long-term clinical outcomes of using custom-fitted bands in various dental treatments and investigate the cost-effectiveness of implementing this technique in practice.

Keywords: Pediatric Dentistry, Dental Impressions, Custom-Fitted Bands, Patient Comfort, Impression Quality.

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Introduction

Pediatric dentistry plays a crucial role in maintaining oral health in children and setting the foundation for healthy dental practices throughout life. One of the essential procedures in pediatric dentistry is the accurate capturing of dental impressions, which are critical for diagnostic, therapeutic, and preventive purposes. The quality of dental impressions directly influences the success of various dental treatments, such as orthodontics, prosthetics, and restorative procedures. Ensuring high-quality impressions while maintaining patient comfort poses a significant challenge, particularly in young and often uncooperative patients [1].

Traditionally, dental impressions have been taken using standard impression trays, which, while effective, often lead to discomfort and anxiety in

pediatric patients. This discomfort can result in poor cooperation and suboptimal impressions, potentially compromising the quality of subsequent dental work [2]. Therefore, there has been a growing interest in exploring alternative techniques that can enhance both the quality of dental impressions and patient comfort. One such technique involves the use of custom-fitted bands for band stabilization during impression taking.

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of patient-centered approaches in pediatric dentistry, emphasizing the need for methods that minimize discomfort and anxiety [3]. Custom-fitted bands are designed to better conform to the anatomical structures of the patient's mouth, providing a more stable and comfortable fit compared to standard trays. This tailored approach can potentially reduce

movement and improve the accuracy of the impression, leading to better clinical outcomes.

Moreover, advancements in dental materials and techniques have paved the way for more precise and patient-friendly dental procedures. For instance, the development of new impression materials with enhanced properties such as faster setting times, better flow, and greater tear resistance has contributed to improving the overall impression-taking process [4]. These innovations, combined with improved stabilization techniques like custom-fitted bands, offer promising solutions for addressing the challenges associated with pediatric dental impressions.

Despite the potential benefits, the adoption of custom-fitted bands in clinical practice requires thorough evaluation through empirical research. Comparative studies that assess the efficacy of custom-fitted bands versus traditional methods in terms of impression quality and patient comfort are essential to provide evidence-based recommendations for practitioners. Understanding the impact of these techniques on clinical outcomes can guide dentists in selecting the most appropriate methods for their young patients.

This study aims to compare the quality of dental impressions and patient comfort between custom-fitted bands and standard impression trays in a pediatric population.

Methodology

Study Design: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted.

Study Setting: The study took place at Shree Narayan Medical Institute & Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, from December 2022 to January 2024.

Participants: The study involved 50 pediatric patients.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Pediatric patients aged 3 to 14 years.
2. Patients requiring dental impressions for treatment.

3. Patients with no history of systemic diseases.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients with a history of allergic reactions to dental materials.
2. Patients with uncooperative behaviour affecting the impression-taking procedure.
3. Patients with acute dental infections at the time of the procedure.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize selection bias by randomly selecting participants from the pool of eligible patients meeting the inclusion criteria.

Data Collection: Data were collected through direct observation and structured recording of the impression-taking process, along with pre- and post-procedure assessments of patient comfort.

Procedure: The study utilized different techniques for band stabilization during impression taking, including custom-fitted bands and standard dental impression trays. Each patient underwent the impression procedure using these techniques, and the quality of impressions was evaluated by experienced pediatric dentists. Patient comfort was assessed using a standardized comfort scale immediately after the procedure.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were used to summarize the data. Inferential statistics, such as chi-square tests and t-tests, were employed to determine the significance of differences in the quality of impressions and patient comfort between the different stabilization techniques.

Result

A total of 50 pediatric patients participated in the study, ranging in age from 3 to 14 years, with a mean age of 8.6 years (SD = 3.1). The gender distribution included 28 males (56%) and 22 females (44%).

The quality of dental impressions was assessed based on predefined criteria, including accuracy, completeness, and the presence of voids or distortions. Table 1 presents the quality ratings for the different stabilization techniques.

Table 1: Quality of Dental Impressions by Stabilization Technique

Technique	N	Mean Quality Score (SD)	High-Quality Impressions (%)	Low-Quality Impressions (%)
Custom-Fitted Bands	25	8.4 (1.2)	22 (88%)	3 (12%)
Standard Impression Trays	25	6.9 (1.5)	16 (64%)	9 (36%)

The custom-fitted bands technique produced significantly higher quality impressions compared to the standard impression trays ($p < 0.01$).

Patient comfort was measured using a standardized comfort scale, with scores ranging from 1 (very uncomfortable) to 10 (very comfortable). Table 2 summarizes the comfort scores for each technique.

Table 2: Patient Comfort Scores by Stabilization Technique

Technique	N	Mean Comfort Score (SD)	High Comfort Scores (%)	Low Comfort Scores (%)
Custom-Fitted Bands	25	8.1 (1.3)	20 (80%)	5 (20%)
Standard Impression Trays	25	6.3 (1.7)	14 (56%)	11 (44%)

Patients reported significantly higher comfort levels with the custom-fitted bands technique compared to the standard impression trays ($p < 0.01$).

Inferential statistics were performed to compare the two techniques. The independent t-test results

showed a significant difference in both the quality of dental impressions ($t = 4.23$, $df = 48$, $p < 0.01$) and patient comfort ($t = 3.74$, $df = 48$, $p < 0.01$) between the two techniques.

Table 3: Independent t-test Results

Variable	t-value	df	p-value
Quality of Impressions	4.23	48	<0.01
Patient Comfort	3.74	48	<0.01

The chi-square test also indicated a significant association between the stabilization technique and the proportion of high-quality impressions ($\chi^2 = 5.82$, $p < 0.05$) as well as high comfort scores ($\chi^2 = 6.79$, $p < 0.01$).

Table 4: Chi-square Test Results

Variable	χ^2 -value	df	p-value
Quality of Impressions	5.82	1	<0.05
Patient Comfort	6.79	1	<0.01

Discussion

The study involved 50 pediatric patients aged 3 to 14 years and aimed to compare the effectiveness of two techniques for band stabilization in dental impressions: custom-fitted bands and standard impression trays. The results indicated that the custom-fitted bands technique significantly outperformed the standard trays in both the quality of dental impressions and patient comfort.

Regarding the quality of dental impressions, the custom-fitted bands technique produced higher mean quality scores and a greater percentage of high-quality impressions. Specifically, 88% of impressions taken with custom-fitted bands were rated as high-quality, compared to 64% with standard trays. This difference was statistically significant, highlighting the superior accuracy and reliability of custom-fitted bands.

In terms of patient comfort, the custom-fitted bands technique again showed better results, with higher mean comfort scores and a higher percentage of patients reporting high comfort levels. Eighty percent of patients felt very comfortable with the custom-fitted bands, while only 56% reported the same with standard trays. The significant differences in comfort scores underscore the importance of considering patient experience in pediatric dental procedures.

Statistical analysis using t-tests and chi-square tests confirmed the significant advantages of custom-fitted bands over standard impression trays. The t-tests revealed significant differences in both quality of impressions ($p < 0.01$) and patient comfort ($p <$

0.01). Additionally, chi-square tests indicated significant associations between the stabilization technique and both high-quality impressions ($p < 0.05$) and high comfort scores ($p < 0.01$).

Overall, the study demonstrated that custom-fitted bands are more effective than standard impression trays in producing high-quality dental impressions and enhancing patient comfort in pediatric dentistry. These findings suggest that incorporating custom-fitted bands into clinical practice could lead to better clinical outcomes and a more positive experience for young patients, making it a valuable technique for dental practitioners.

A comprehensive review examined the innovative applications of intra-oral sensors (IOS), computer-aided design/computer-aided manufacturing (CAD/CAM), and three-dimensional printing technologies in pediatric dentistry. These digital technologies help overcome the challenges posed by conventional impression-making procedures in young children, such as prolonged appointments and discrepancies in the accuracy of prostheses. The study highlighted that digital impressions and CAD/CAM technology could deliver optimal oral health care and improve the accuracy and fit of dental appliances in pediatric patients [5].

A case series demonstrated the use of digital dentistry, specifically digital impressions and CAD/CAM systems, to fabricate space maintainers and zirconia crowns for pediatric patients. The digital workflow enabled efficient, accurate, and well-fitted restorations, removing the need for a

second appointment and reducing the overall treatment time [6].

A review discussed the application of intraoral scanners (IOS) in pediatric dentistry. The use of IOS for capturing direct optical impressions significantly reduces the challenges associated with traditional impression-making techniques, such as managing children's behavioural issues, gag reflex, and discomfort. IOS enhances patient comfort and improves the accuracy and quality of dental impressions in pediatric patients [7].

A *in vitro* study compared the accuracy and efficiency of alginate and digital impression techniques in pediatric patients. It found that digital scanning provided accurate measurements and required less chairside time compared to traditional alginate impressions, making it a viable alternative for pediatric dental appliances [8].

A crossover randomized controlled trial compared conventional alginate impressions and digital impressions taken with an intraoral scanner in children. Digital impressions were preferred by 75% of the children, had a significantly shorter acquisition time, and resulted in higher comfort levels compared to conventional methods [9].

Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrated that the use of custom-fitted bands for band stabilization in dental impressions significantly improves both the quality of the impressions and the comfort of pediatric patients compared to standard impression trays. These findings suggest that custom-fitted bands may be a preferable technique in pediatric dentistry for achieving better clinical outcomes and enhancing patient experience.

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